

Facing the Challenges of Future Optical Metro Networks: Programmable Modular Multi-Tb/s Photonic System Architectures

The metropolitan area network (MAN) segment is becoming one of the most challenging due to the ever increasing volume and dynamicity of traffic, induced by novel and bandwidth-hungry services and applications as well as the need for instant data access in our globally-networked and hyperconnected society. In addition to the ultra-high capacity and dynamic scenario, another challenge is related to the stringent requirements in terms of both capital and operational expenditures (CAPEX/OPEX). Particularly in the MAN, the reduction of cost, power consumption and footprint is of paramount importance. In order to efficiently and cost-effectively support the required ultra-broadband transport featuring dynamic capacity adaptation, suitable technologies should be specifically designed and tailored for the MAN segment. In this talk, programmable modular architectures and photonic technologies to address the challenges of future ultra-high capacity and agile MAN will be presented. In particular, an overview of the solutions envisioned and developed within the H2020 European PASSION project will be described, with special emphasis on the programmable modular system architecture adopting vertical cavity surface emitting laser (VCSEL) technology, coherent receiver and photonic integration. By exploiting both spectral and spatial dimensions multi-Tb/s capacity can be attained in a dynamic MAN scenario.